

1 **Supplementary Material**

2 **Higher intelligence is genetically linked with longevity**

3 Mousumee Khan^{1,3}, Enkhchimeg Lkhagva^{1,3}, Sharif Hasan Siddiqui² and Seong-Tshool Hong^{1*}

4 ¹Department of Biomedical Sciences and Institute for Medical Science, Jeonbuk National
5 University Medical School, Jeonju, Jeonbuk 54907, South Korea.

6 ²Department of Animal Biotechnology, College of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Jeonbuk
7 National University, Jeonju, Jeonbuk 54896, South Korea.

8 ³These authors contributed equally: Mousumee Khan, Enkhchimeg Lkhagva.

9 *corresponding author. Email: seonghong@jbnu.ac.kr

10

11 Supplementary Figure S1. Graphical experimental design of the study.

12

13 Supplementary Figure S2. The lifespan of *D. melanogaster* at each generation during the
 14 intelligence selection. a) The survival curve of the NINT male and female *D. melanogaster*.
 15 b) The survival curve of the INT male and female *D. melanogaster*. The lifespan is
 16 represented by the Kaplan-Meier survival method.

17

18 Supplementary Figure S3. The representative H&E-stained brain sections of *D. melanogaster*
19 scoring the degree of neurodegeneration. Histological sections of the brains were scored from
20 0 to 5 based on the severity of the neurodegeneration by measuring the number of vacuoles as
21 well as their damaged tissue area. Higher score represents a more severe neurodegeneration.
22 Representative images of the H&E-stained brain sections corresponding to each score are as
23 follows: 0, 1 normal to low; 2, 3 moderates; 4, 5 strong to severe.

Male

Female

24

25 Supplementary Figure S4. The representative H&E-stained histological images of the
26 medullas male and female *D. melanogaster* with age progression. Stained medulla tissues
27 were observed at the magnification of 400X. Scale bar, 50 μm .

28

29 Supplementary Figure S5. The representative H&E-stained histological images the flight
 30 muscles of male and female *D. melanogaster* with age progression. A longitudinal-sections
 31 and B cross-sections of the flight muscles of male and female *D. melanogaster* with age
 32 progression. Stained flight muscle tissues were observed at the magnification of 100X. Scale
 33 bar, 50 μ m.

Male

Female

34

35 Supplementary Figure S6. The startle-induced negative geotaxis assay of male and female *D.*

36 *melanogaster* with age progression. The startle-induced negative geotaxis assay of male and

37 female *D. melanogaster* with age progression. All data were statistically analyzed by an

38 unpaired Student's t-test, and values are shown as mean $\pm$ SE. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ and

39 *** $P < 0.001$.

Male

Female

40

41 Supplementary Figure S7. Body weight difference of male and female *D. melanogaster* with
42 age progression. All data were statistically analyzed by an unpaired Student's t-test, and
43 values are shown as mean $\pm$ SE. * $P < 0.05$ and ** $P < 0.01$.

44

45 Supplementary Figure S8. The bioanalyzer quality control data. a, c) The migration pattern of
 46 the total mRNA of male (a) and female (c) *D. melanogaster*. b, d) The peak pattern of the tot
 47 al mRNA of male (b) and female (d) *D. melanogaster*.

48

49 Supplementary Figure S9. The schematic illustration of total mRNA sequenci

a)

b)

c)

50

51 Supplementary Figure S10. The principal component analysis (PCA) for RNA-seq sample
52 quality. a- c The principal component analysis (PCA) for RNA-seq sample quality for each
53 comparison group. INT-F₀: INT compared to F₀ (a), NINT-F₀: NINT compared to F₀ (b) and
54 INT- NINT: INT compared to NINT (c).

55

Supplementary Tables

56 Supplementary Table S1. List of the fly strains used to establish F₀ generation

Strain	Genotype	Source
Oregon-R-C	Oregon-R-C	BDSC# 5
DGRP-100	DGRP-100	BDSC# 55017
BER_2	BER_2	BDSC# 3840
Harwich	Harwich	BDSC# 4264
Canton-S	Canton-S	BDSC# 64349
Wild_1A	Wild_1A	BDSC# 3878
w[1118]	w ¹¹¹⁸	BDSC# 5905
<i>multiple wing hairs (mwh)</i>	<u><i>mwh</i></u>	
<i>flare3 (flr³)</i>	<i>flr3/In(3LR)TM3, ri p^p sep l(3)89Aa bx^{34e} e Bd^S</i>	
<i>Oregon R flare3 (ORR, flr³)</i>	<i>ORR; flr3/In(3LR)TM3, ri p^p sep l(3)89Aa bx^{34e} e Bd^S</i>	

57

58 Supplementary Table S2. The composition of *Drosophila* standard cornmeal–agar–molasses
59 medium (for 1 Liter)

Ingredients	Amount
Corn meal	84 gm
Yeast	24 gm
Sucrose	47 gm
Agar*	6/8 gm
Distilled water	1 liter
Molasses	25 ml
10% methyl parahydroxybenzoate	10 ml
Propionic acid	4 ml

60 * Agar is needed in the amount of 6gm and 8 gm in soft and hard medium, respectively.

61 Supplementary Table S3. The quality data of male mRNA used for total mRNA sequencing
 62 (RNA extraction quality)

Sample	Fly numbers	Age (Days)	Conc. (ng μl^{-1})	Total (μg)	OD_{260/280}	OD_{260/230}	RIN	Result
F ₀ -1	100	5	1934.4	218.587	2.15	1.58	6.3	Pass
F ₀ -2	100	5	2036.4	228.081	2.14	1.35	6.3	Pass
F ₀ -3	100	5	1538.2	169.199	2.17	1.76	6.4	Pass
INT-1	100	5	3261.0	101.090	2.03	1.99	5.1	Pass
INT-2	100	5	2958.8	91.722	2.10	2.05	6.1	Pass
INT-3	100	5	2841.7	88.092	2.08	2.05	5.9	Pass
NINT-1	100	5	3489.8	108.183	2.01	2.24	4.9	Pass
NINT-2	100	5	3573.3	110.774	1.98	2.03	6.1	Pass
NINT-3	100	5	3488.3	108.137	2.01	2.05	6.0	Pass

63

64 Supplementary Table S4. The quality data of female mRNA used for total mRNA sequencing
 65 (RNA extraction quality)

Sample	Fly numbers	Age (Days)	Conc. (ng μl^{-1})	Total (μg)	OD_{260/280}	OD_{260/230}	RIN	Result
F ₀ -1	100	5	3994.9	439.437	1.58	1.32	6.5	Pass
F ₀ -2	100	5	3631.7	406.754	1.95	1.40	6.3	Pass
F ₀ -3	100	5	3752.1	423.985	1.90	1.34	6.4	Pass
INT-1	100	5	3018.3	87.53	2.02	2.20	6.5	Pass
INT-2	100	5	4108.1	119.13	1.89	2.01	6.9	Pass
INT-3	100	5	3756.1	108.93	1.94	2.06	7.3	Pass
NINT-1	100	5	3833.6	191.68	1.89	2.01	6.3	Pass
NINT-2	100	5	3768.4	188.42	1.90	2.01	6.3	Pass
NINT-3	100	5	4238.4	211.92	1.93	2.05	6.3	Pass

66

67 Supplementary Table S5. The list of the upregulated genes in each population

INT (compared with F₀)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
56	Acp24A4	2951.112	11.720	1.821	6.436	1.23E-10	1.44E-07
55	Ser12	78.197	9.029	1.855	4.867	1.13E-06	4.04E-04
54	CR31084	334.968	7.543	0.799	9.445	3.54E-21	2.90E-17
53	CG42876	40.805	7.046	1.215	5.800	6.62E-09	4.72281E-06
52	CR45530	2689.245	6.305	1.327	4.752	2.01E-06	6.87E-04
51	CR44463	9.070	5.998	1.308	4.584	4.55E-06	0.001287735
50	CG7542	1517.173	4.425	0.581	7.616	2.61E-14	5.36E-11
49	CG4927	66.973	4.233	0.809	5.235	1.65E-07	7.95E-05
48	CG43165	13.065	4.191	1.003	4.178	2.94E-05	6.04E-03
47	CR43452	10.325	4.130	0.832	4.964	6.89E-07	2.76E-04
46	Cyp6a8	146.870	4.003	0.640	6.251	4.08E-10	4.1789E-07
45	CG4757	692.579	3.598	0.661	5.441	5.30E-08	2.81E-05
44	CG34291	532.532	3.588	0.845	4.247	2.17E-05	4.77E-03
43	CG10725	432.713	3.344	0.541	6.177	6.54E-10	6.26E-07
42	CG11034	992.056	3.308	0.313	10.584	3.55E-26	5.82E-22
41	CG2772	209.525	3.291	0.536	6.140	8.27E-10	7.14E-07
40	CG11893	253.204	3.018	0.473	6.376	1.82E-10	1.99E-07
39	CG10140	12.225	2.923	0.669	4.367	1.26E-05	2.99E-03
38	CG13324	385.953	2.753	0.551	4.996	5.85E-07	2.46E-04
37	CG8539	238.201	2.680	0.305	8.782	1.61E-18	6.60E-15
36	CG11700	2357.666	2.679	0.538	4.976	6.49E-07	2.66E-04
35	CR43651	133.288	2.480	0.335	7.408	1.29E-13	2.11E-10
34	CG13454	9.840	2.464	0.529	4.659	3.18E-06	9.48E-04
33	CG33337	15.856	2.244	0.497	4.515	6.33E-06	1.73E-03
32	CG16704	421.585	2.122	0.435	4.876	1.08E-06	3.94E-04
31	CG42329	143.440	1.799	0.371	4.854	1.21068E-06	0.000422604
30	CG12204	445.390	1.766	0.257	6.864	6.72E-12	8.47509E-09
29	CR42861	164.493	1.657	0.350	4.730	2.25E-06	0.000723346
28	CG33774	386.998	1.579	0.259	6.087	1.15E-09	9.42574E-07
27	CG32641	1415.952	1.528	0.190	8.052	8.14E-16	2.65636E-12
26	CR44030	235.266	1.416	0.315	4.498	6.86E-06	0.001844422
25	CG14120	1598.932	1.355	0.329	4.114	3.90E-05	0.007890338
24	CG8768	301.080	1.355	0.147	9.243	2.39E-20	1.30508E-16
23	CG14820	517.789	1.266	0.300	4.223	2.42E-05	0.005213584
22	GstD3	184.374	1.240	0.305	4.065	4.81E-05	9.29E-03
21	Thor	6842.719	1.176	0.287	4.092	4.28E-05	0.008459205
20	fuss	265.884	1.129	0.207	5.459	4.79E-08	2.62E-05

19	CG32581	2402.815	1.079	0.182	5.942	2.82E-09	2.10391E-06
18	CG32640	1384.636	1.013	0.164	6.169	6.87E-10	6.26371E-07
17	snoRNA:Or-CD11a	4784.590	0.978	0.190	5.147	2.65E-07	0.0001241
16	snoRNA:Or-CD11c	13618.260	0.976	0.199	4.906	9.31E-07	0.000347044
15	snoRNA:Or-CD11b	13618.272	0.976	0.199	4.906	9.30E-07	0.000347044
14	CG41378	498.083	0.966	0.216	4.481	7.44E-06	0.001968984
13	CG6852	1519.523	0.956	0.132	7.237	4.58E-13	6.83E-10
12	snoRNA:Psi28S-1232	1236.101	0.949	0.173	5.495	3.91E-08	2.21352E-05
11	CG18417	283.237	0.922	0.165	5.577	2.45E-08	1.55E-05
10	CG6094	436.089	0.841	0.200	4.197	2.70E-05	5.63E-03
9	CG7054	933.555	0.833	0.198	4.201	2.65E-05	0.005633635
8	CG9577	1129.868	0.769	0.103	7.451	9.24E-14	1.68524E-10
7	snoRNA:Psi18S-920	6624.396	0.675	0.146	4.616	3.91E-06	0.001144926
6	Bet5	277.068	0.536	0.131	4.096	4.20E-05	0.008394285
5	CG15432	553.003	0.506	0.120	4.196	2.71E-05	0.005633635
4	CG7456	1107.933	0.491	0.104	4.712	2.46E-06	7.71E-04
3	GM130	1130.337	0.432	0.078	5.523	3.34E-08	1.96E-05
2	CG30118	5658.622	0.411	0.074	5.542	2.99E-08	1.82E-05
1	P5cr	465.193	0.381	0.090	4.246	2.18E-05	0.004768501

NINT (compared with F₀)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
152	Acp24A4	2951.112	10.022	1.821	5.504	3.719E-08	6.780E-06
151	Ser12	78.197	9.388	1.855	5.062	4.158E-07	5.016E-05
150	CG42876	40.805	8.291	1.212	6.842	7.783E-12	5.804E-09
149	Obp47b	149.550	8.013	1.615	4.962	6.961E-07	7.465E-05
148	CR31084	334.968	7.942	0.798	9.949	2.554E-23	4.191E-19
147	Or47b	301.666	7.585	1.517	5.000	5.746E-07	6.434E-05
146	sha	1929.002	7.302	1.326	5.509	3.608E-08	6.650E-06
145	Cpr5C	10.272	6.514	1.778	3.664	2.481E-04	7.934E-03
144	CR44463	9.070	6.221	1.305	4.769	1.852E-06	1.726E-04
143	CG4757	692.579	5.261	0.661	7.962	1.688E-15	2.518E-12
142	nompA	1136.894	5.123	1.014	5.055	4.302E-07	5.152E-05
141	CG30098	15.838	5.052	1.091	4.632	3.616E-06	2.951E-04
140	CG42729	4.833	5.001	1.027	4.868	1.128E-06	1.102E-04
139	CG43165	13.065	4.667	0.998	4.677	2.905E-06	2.508E-04
138	CG13324	385.953	4.667	0.550	8.488	2.099E-17	8.607E-14
137	CG4927	66.973	4.596	0.807	5.692	1.258E-08	2.680E-06
136	CG42728	5.022	4.503	0.967	4.659	3.184E-06	2.671E-04
135	CG11313	143.923	4.137	0.897	4.615	3.932E-06	3.162E-04

134	CR44371	9.798	4.106	1.048	3.919	8.904E-05	3.652E-03
133	CG7542	1517.173	4.104	0.581	7.064	1.617E-12	1.474E-09
132	Desat2	125.359	3.955	0.856	4.618	3.877E-06	3.133E-04
131	CG34291	532.532	3.941	0.845	4.666	3.064E-06	2.618E-04
130	CG10725	432.713	3.878	0.541	7.169	7.565E-13	7.757E-10
129	CG13646	12.220	3.836	0.916	4.187	2.829E-05	1.532E-03
128	Cyp6a8	146.870	3.813	0.640	5.957	2.577E-09	7.046E-07
127	CR44640	18.033	3.601	0.890	4.048	5.166E-05	2.354E-03
126	CG12708	103.151	3.597	0.771	4.668	3.035E-06	2.607E-04
125	CG14329	16.504	3.581	0.882	4.060	4.914E-05	2.284E-03
124	CG7741	2210.587	3.574	0.762	4.693	2.696E-06	2.365E-04
123	TotM	149.558	3.538	0.606	5.843	5.114E-09	1.234E-06
122	CG10140	12.225	3.483	0.660	5.279	1.300E-07	1.918E-05
121	Cda9	308.702	3.459	0.761	4.544	5.522E-06	4.137E-04
120	Ir40a	58.784	3.410	0.701	4.868	1.126E-06	1.102E-04
119	CG13905	680.004	3.347	0.597	5.607	2.053E-08	4.066E-06
118	CG17191	20.598	3.227	0.819	3.939	8.181E-05	3.372E-03
117	CR43857	38.537	3.120	0.695	4.493	7.028E-06	5.057E-04
116	Sox21a	54.647	3.109	0.747	4.161	3.172E-05	1.673E-03
115	CG11893	253.204	3.096	0.473	6.544	5.971E-11	2.721E-08
114	CG33137	13.435	3.092	0.838	3.690	2.240E-04	7.365E-03
113	CG30033	411.798	3.090	0.715	4.324	1.531E-05	9.586E-04
112	CG2772	209.525	3.053	0.536	5.696	1.227E-08	2.648E-06
111	CG11034	992.056	2.961	0.313	9.472	2.740E-21	2.248E-17
110	CR43651	133.288	2.952	0.333	8.861	7.956E-19	4.351E-15
109	CG12970	28.386	2.913	0.696	4.187	2.826E-05	1.532E-03
108	CG32302	109.913	2.864	0.549	5.214	1.846E-07	2.503E-05
107	CG16704	421.585	2.812	0.435	6.470	9.807E-11	4.234E-08
106	CG9759	593.736	2.677	0.694	3.860	1.134E-04	4.440E-03
105	CG13461	29.497	2.620	0.715	3.662	2.500E-04	7.965E-03
104	CG8539	238.201	2.493	0.305	8.173	3.007E-16	6.167E-13
103	CG43773	51.666	2.489	0.425	5.861	4.612E-09	1.146E-06
102	CG33337	15.856	2.456	0.491	5.004	5.624E-07	6.363E-05
101	CG43187	29.348	2.425	0.495	4.899	9.621E-07	9.743E-05
100	CR42646	57.872	2.383	0.662	3.599	3.194E-04	9.614E-03
99	CG32284	144.802	2.362	0.599	3.941	8.110E-05	3.360E-03
98	CR45045	188.460	2.348	0.607	3.866	1.107E-04	4.376E-03
97	Osi8	26.236	2.092	0.550	3.804	1.423E-04	5.245E-03
96	CR42874	9.002	2.022	0.531	3.804	1.421E-04	5.245E-03
95	CG12520	32.026	1.991	0.441	4.512	6.411E-06	4.695E-04
94	Sox100B	80.542	1.913	0.475	4.025	5.703E-05	2.515E-03
93	Npc2e	548.008	1.868	0.479	3.902	9.531E-05	3.871E-03

92	Damm	1115.414	1.853	0.493	3.759	1.708E-04	5.944E-03
91	CG3259	64.863	1.808	0.456	3.966	7.305E-05	3.081E-03
90	CG4259	314.122	1.764	0.395	4.465	7.991E-06	5.607E-04
89	CR42861	164.493	1.760	0.350	5.033	4.826E-07	5.656E-05
88	CG11261	261.255	1.712	0.315	5.431	5.603E-08	9.677E-06
87	CG12204	445.390	1.708	0.257	6.647	2.995E-11	1.820E-08
86	CG42329	143.440	1.621	0.370	4.377	1.205E-05	7.939E-04
85	GstD3	184.374	1.571	0.304	5.169	2.354E-07	3.090E-05
84	CR44192	618.494	1.535	0.341	4.503	6.689E-06	4.855E-04
83	CG32641	1415.952	1.508	0.190	7.952	1.842E-15	2.519E-12
82	CR44030	235.266	1.501	0.314	4.776	1.784E-06	1.672E-04
81	CG1529	893.262	1.498	0.364	4.117	3.839E-05	1.903E-03
80	CG33774	386.998	1.471	0.259	5.679	1.354E-08	2.848E-06
79	CG13902	297.886	1.411	0.318	4.430	9.442E-06	6.454E-04
78	CG11842	398.640	1.396	0.383	3.640	2.729E-04	8.529E-03
77	fuss	265.884	1.326	0.206	6.442	1.180E-10	4.609E-08
76	Cht8	1073.713	1.253	0.227	5.526	3.278E-08	6.182E-06
75	snoRNA:Me28S-C788b	84.199	1.135	0.232	4.895	9.828E-07	9.842E-05
74	CG11695	518.250	1.117	0.311	3.593	3.264E-04	9.772E-03
73	l(2)not	573.352	1.111	0.290	3.829	1.288E-04	4.901E-03
72	CR45341	46.993	1.101	0.268	4.104	4.064E-05	1.977E-03
71	dgo	323.496	1.069	0.232	4.605	4.123E-06	3.236E-04
70	gny	234.429	1.067	0.178	6.002	1.950E-09	5.714E-07
69	Thor	6842.719	1.048	0.287	3.647	2.653E-04	8.370E-03
68	CG8768	301.080	1.043	0.146	7.122	1.061E-12	1.024E-09
67	CG5773	1754.914	1.025	0.247	4.144	3.418E-05	1.741E-03
66	CG14906	215.015	1.018	0.233	4.372	1.232E-05	8.086E-04
65	CG32581	2402.815	1.018	0.182	5.607	2.057E-08	4.066E-06
64	CG13102	518.128	1.015	0.222	4.565	4.994E-06	3.811E-04
63	CG4496	249.846	0.974	0.251	3.880	1.046E-04	4.153E-03
62	CG31075	1553.636	0.974	0.226	4.308	1.648E-05	1.012E-03
61	CG6852	1519.523	0.959	0.132	7.271	3.556E-13	3.889E-10
60	CG6928	840.026	0.959	0.231	4.152	3.295E-05	1.705E-03
59	CR31514	125.127	0.955	0.257	3.712	2.060E-04	6.883E-03
58	CG32640	1384.636	0.950	0.164	5.792	6.959E-09	1.608E-06
57	CG6094	436.089	0.880	0.200	4.402	1.071E-05	7.175E-04
56	CG32537	442.757	0.870	0.204	4.276	1.899E-05	1.120E-03
54	CG9960	354.645	0.867	0.166	5.229	1.705E-07	2.331E-05
55	Snapin	354.645	0.867	0.166	5.229	1.705E-07	2.331E-05
53	CG43320	156.490	0.861	0.232	3.710	2.073E-04	6.899E-03
52	CG6201	280.408	0.856	0.211	4.055	5.011E-05	2.317E-03

51	O-fut2	538.309	0.855	0.234	3.654	2.586E-04	8.189E-03
50	Pvf1	983.867	0.851	0.171	4.988	6.110E-07	6.727E-05
49	CG9577	1129.868	0.821	0.103	7.983	1.433E-15	2.350E-12
48	omd	1521.315	0.816	0.217	3.760	1.700E-04	5.935E-03
47	CG9723	694.005	0.808	0.188	4.291	1.779E-05	1.069E-03
46	sgl	2121.675	0.805	0.207	3.899	9.668E-05	3.911E-03
45	CG18417	283.237	0.778	0.165	4.720	2.357E-06	2.102E-04
44	CG8449	958.927	0.754	0.176	4.277	1.898E-05	1.120E-03
43	CG18596	761.742	0.745	0.157	4.738	2.164E-06	1.950E-04
42	CG31344	326.013	0.744	0.200	3.727	1.938E-04	6.556E-03
41	CG7054	933.555	0.737	0.198	3.719	1.998E-04	6.704E-03
40	spict	771.656	0.732	0.105	6.986	2.822E-12	2.315E-09
39	CG4557	995.225	0.729	0.197	3.707	2.101E-04	6.972E-03
38	ash2	908.546	0.705	0.170	4.146	3.387E-05	1.731E-03
37	CalpC	415.048	0.703	0.162	4.336	1.449E-05	9.286E-04
36	CG5590	1605.657	0.702	0.119	5.911	3.406E-09	9.014E-07
35	CG7456	1107.933	0.699	0.104	6.735	1.638E-11	1.120E-08
34	CG12237	1050.910	0.692	0.175	3.963	7.387E-05	3.108E-03
33	sinu	550.984	0.691	0.173	3.994	6.499E-05	2.784E-03
32	isoQC	646.011	0.685	0.134	5.109	3.243E-07	4.125E-05
31	Aats-pro	382.941	0.663	0.177	3.751	1.764E-04	6.106E-03
30	CG8195	468.063	0.636	0.171	3.717	2.020E-04	6.762E-03
29	CG18476	338.801	0.631	0.152	4.157	3.218E-05	1.680E-03
28	Ef1alpha48D	412025.142	0.623	0.157	3.969	7.208E-05	3.048E-03
27	trbl	1262.853	0.618	0.163	3.783	1.551E-04	5.604E-03
26	Trs23	222.424	0.614	0.163	3.781	1.565E-04	5.617E-03
25	CG13369	1223.838	0.600	0.160	3.758	1.710E-04	5.944E-03
24	Mvl	2735.297	0.582	0.150	3.877	1.056E-04	4.187E-03
23	Ipk1	354.774	0.564	0.154	3.676	2.372E-04	7.707E-03
22	CG12772	715.663	0.563	0.133	4.233	2.309E-05	1.296E-03
21	CR44047	1042.096	0.562	0.104	5.426	5.764E-08	9.851E-06
20	CG18011	385.832	0.560	0.114	4.932	8.127E-07	8.385E-05
19	loj	1177.930	0.550	0.118	4.682	2.845E-06	2.470E-04
18	pix	7608.154	0.546	0.116	4.721	2.342E-06	2.099E-04
17	AdSS	5866.285	0.546	0.104	5.267	1.387E-07	1.962E-05
16	CR43872	621.290	0.539	0.130	4.148	3.351E-05	1.723E-03
15	SH3PX1	1270.434	0.498	0.130	3.830	1.280E-04	4.892E-03
14	crq	3459.380	0.488	0.115	4.235	2.282E-05	1.294E-03
13	Ate1	1188.668	0.482	0.108	4.471	7.777E-06	5.500E-04
12	P5cr	465.193	0.472	0.088	5.340	9.300E-08	1.467E-05
11	CG5168	2178.283	0.446	0.117	3.798	1.457E-04	5.312E-03
10	qm	622.400	0.443	0.104	4.242	2.216E-05	1.271E-03

9	Vamp7	1555.340	0.439	0.106	4.152	3.293E-05	1.705E-03
8	cert	1637.451	0.437	0.108	4.054	5.043E-05	2.324E-03
7	AdenoK	3316.757	0.424	0.069	6.175	6.600E-10	2.166E-07
6	RagC-D	942.636	0.417	0.101	4.132	3.589E-05	1.801E-03
5	GM130	1130.337	0.410	0.078	5.269	1.371E-07	1.962E-05
4	CG8726	1579.713	0.385	0.101	3.816	1.358E-04	5.074E-03
3	TfIIA-L	1828.207	0.370	0.094	3.944	8.000E-05	3.331E-03
2	CR44390	494.579	0.305	0.069	4.437	9.104E-06	6.250E-04
1	Gie	920.899	0.288	0.075	3.847	1.196E-04	4.617E-03

INT (compared with NINT)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
36	Cpr65Ax2	83.141	24.741	2.880	8.590	8.692E-18	1.398E-13
35	Acp1	10432.825	8.461	1.445	5.857	4.720E-09	1.898E-05
34	CR45530	2689.245	8.202	1.330	6.169	6.860E-10	5.518E-06
33	CG10591	29.419	8.126	1.630	4.985	6.195E-07	9.060E-04
32	Acp65Aa	1710.694	7.277	1.438	5.060	4.185E-07	6.732E-04
31	CG8736	4655.404	7.093	1.525	4.652	3.292E-06	2.207E-03
30	CG7214	4545.898	7.057	1.342	5.258	1.454E-07	2.923E-04
29	Cpr92F	2193.871	6.633	1.455	4.558	5.161E-06	3.075E-03
28	CG13731	293.951	6.501	1.320	4.924	8.497E-07	1.139E-03
27	Ccp84Ab	126.683	6.205	1.310	4.735	2.186E-06	1.599E-03
26	CG13041	34.860	6.141	1.136	5.408	6.376E-08	1.465E-04
25	fln	11224.318	6.089	1.269	4.799	1.594E-06	1.371E-03
24	CR45161	3966.659	6.022	1.258	4.786	1.705E-06	1.371E-03
23	Osi7	105.886	5.907	1.326	4.455	8.402E-06	4.661E-03
22	CG13060	13.996	5.603	1.299	4.313	1.612E-05	7.264E-03
21	CG7203	12872.581	5.444	1.153	4.721	2.343E-06	1.639E-03
20	CR45663	20.275	5.344	1.048	5.101	3.38E-07	6.035E-04
19	CG15617	424.562	4.893	1.135	4.311	1.63E-05	7.264E-03
18	CG13026	115.197	4.397	0.913	4.818	1.45E-06	1.371E-03
17	Scp1	30418.593	3.555	0.638	5.568	2.58E-08	6.908E-05
16	Osi9	33.401	2.348	0.531	4.419	9.92E-06	5.321E-03
15	mag	3776.051	1.836	0.383	4.790	1.67E-06	1.371E-03
14	CG4461	1655.760	1.049	0.175	5.999	1.98E-09	1.063E-05
13	Obp19a	311.336	1.021	0.223	4.574	4.79E-06	2.966E-03
2	CG7580	19980.190	0.876	0.194	4.521	6.14E-06	3.530E-03
1	Mf	46470.056	0.804	0.169	4.742	2.11E-06	1.599E-03

69 Supplementary Table 6. The list of the downregulated genes in each population

INT (compared with F₀)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
1	Fbp1	380.875	-7.879	1.570	-5.020	5.18E-07	0.000223453
2	Fbp2	226.509	-5.946	1.049	-5.667	1.46E-08	9.56E-06
3	CG17147	350.700	-4.486	0.559	-8.030	9.71E-16	2.66E-12
4	MtnB	1153.489	-3.381	0.468	-7.223	5.08E-13	6.94E-10
5	CG43218	123.374	-2.994	0.582	-5.141	2.74E-07	0.000124753
6	CG15597	26.856	-2.909	0.614	-4.738	2.16E-06	0.000715026
7	CG17145	26.105	-2.345	0.524	-4.471	7.79E-06	0.002028365
8	CG33639	157.631	-1.751	0.405	-4.321	1.55E-05	0.003643831
9	CG12672	35.799	-1.645	0.373	-4.414	1.01E-05	0.002519725
10	CG1304	544.845	-1.552	0.201	-7.723	1.14E-14	2.66E-11
11	CG8628	3735.722	-1.534	0.293	-5.237	1.63E-07	7.95E-05
12	CG11320	27.807	-1.508	0.327	-4.610	4.03E-06	0.001159209
13	CG18107	814.713	-1.448	0.241	-6.007	1.89E-09	1.47E-06
14	CG14854	63.351	-1.358	0.316	-4.294	1.75E-05	0.003998107
15	PGRP-SC2	4067.493	-1.313	0.297	-4.426	9.59E-06	0.00245859
16	CG5999	178.952	-1.230	0.280	-4.396	1.10E-05	0.002694378
17	Ser6	892.930	-1.207	0.298	-4.053	5.05E-05	0.009631828
18	CR43719	58.449	-1.198	0.278	-4.312	1.62E-05	0.003732435
19	udd	646.532	-1.105	0.235	-4.709	2.49E-06	0.000770876
20	CG18853	1568.274	-1.000	0.176	-5.673	1.40E-08	9.56E-06
21	mRpL27	1313.804	-0.876	0.185	-4.736	2.18E-06	0.000715026
22	CG3603	571.208	-0.789	0.145	-5.427	5.72E-08	2.93E-05
23	CG6084	6772.871	-0.789	0.160	-4.926	8.38E-07	0.000327259
24	mir-4967	86.893	-0.724	0.154	-4.693	2.69E-06	0.00081636
25	Gip	1953.270	-0.714	0.161	-4.419	9.93E-06	0.002505318
26	CG32500	1283.226	-0.701	0.138	-5.065	4.08E-07	0.000180893
27	CG10444	1172.959	-0.699	0.163	-4.280	1.87E-05	0.004195577
28	CG14606	194.131	-0.608	0.150	-4.065	4.80E-05	0.009288681
29	CG33502	6281.878	-0.582	0.133	-4.387	1.15E-05	0.002770558
30	Etf-QO	2429.156	-0.409	0.089	-4.577	4.72E-06	0.001313228

NINT (compared with F₀)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
1	Cpr65Ax2	83.141	-24.273	2.880	-8.427	3.54E-17	1.16E-13
2	Acp1	10432.825	-11.322	1.445	-7.837	4.61E-15	5.82E-12
3	Fbp1	380.875	-10.909	1.700	-6.418	1.38E-10	5.25E-08
4	CG5172	1602.552	-10.123	1.882	-5.378	7.55E-08	1.24E-05
5	Acp65Aa	1710.694	-10.085	1.438	-7.014	2.32E-12	2.00E-09

6	CG7214	4545.898	-9.852	1.342	-7.341	2.12E-13	2.48E-10
7	CG8736	4655.404	-9.700	1.525	-6.362	2.00E-10	7.44E-08
8	CG17298	801.833	-9.605	1.563	-6.146	7.94E-10	2.55E-07
9	Cpr92F	2193.871	-9.593	1.455	-6.593	4.32E-11	2.26E-08
10	CG13065	126.642	-9.563	1.749	-5.466	4.59E-08	8.19E-06
11	CG13043	161.138	-9.458	1.800	-5.253	1.49E-07	2.09E-05
12	CG12998	4329.768	-9.140	1.818	-5.027	4.97E-07	5.79E-05
13	CG11458	677.600	-9.121	1.364	-6.687	2.27E-11	1.43E-08
14	Cpr97Ea	464.816	-9.000	1.589	-5.665	1.47E-08	3.02E-06
15	CG31862	42.950	-8.780	2.232	-3.933	8.39E-05	0.003449276
16	CG13731	293.951	-8.748	1.320	-6.630	3.36E-11	1.97E-08
17	fln	11224.318	-8.686	1.269	-6.846	7.59E-12	5.80E-09
18	CG13042	63.359	-8.684	1.687	-5.147	2.65E-07	3.42E-05
19	CR45161	3966.659	-8.535	1.258	-6.782	1.18E-11	8.43E-09
20	TwdlN	26.558	-8.170	2.044	-3.997	6.41E-05	0.002760472
21	Cpr62Bc	1823.593	-8.077	1.273	-6.343	2.26E-10	7.87E-08
22	CG34248	15.368	-8.010	1.724	-4.647	3.37E-06	0.00027935
23	Ccp84Ab	126.683	-7.983	1.309	-6.098	1.07E-09	3.25E-07
24	Act88F	29717.179	-7.793	1.261	-6.178	6.50E-10	2.17E-07
25	CG7203	12872.581	-7.630	1.153	-6.616	3.68E-11	2.04E-08
26	CG34327	1114.960	-7.542	1.404	-5.371	7.83E-08	1.26E-05
27	Cpr47Ea	557.072	-7.415	1.128	-6.573	4.92E-11	2.41E-08
28	CG13041	34.860	-7.387	1.132	-6.524	6.85E-11	3.04E-08
29	Cpr100A	3112.369	-7.230	1.264	-5.720	1.07E-08	2.37E-06
30	CG10591	29.419	-6.914	1.633	-4.235	2.29E-05	0.001294219
31	Fbp2	226.509	-6.833	1.057	-6.466	1.01E-10	4.24E-08
32	TpnC4	3337.114	-6.808	1.140	-5.974	2.32E-09	6.55E-07
33	CG15617	424.562	-6.682	1.135	-5.890	3.87E-09	9.92E-07
34	CR45663	20.275	-6.613	1.041	-6.350	2.15E-10	7.69E-08
35	Nlp3	16267.039	-6.564	0.992	-6.614	3.73E-11	2.04E-08
36	Osi15	25.512	-6.529	1.797	-3.634	0.000279227	0.008683185
37	CG13060	13.996	-6.441	1.295	-4.975	6.51E-07	7.08E-05
38	TwdlM	77.695	-6.441	1.546	-4.167	3.08E-05	0.001641136
39	Cpr49Ah	203.432	-6.318	1.277	-4.949	7.48E-07	7.86E-05
40	Pxd	249.758	-6.270	1.346	-4.658	3.19E-06	0.000267126
41	CG2150	29.257	-6.222	1.310	-4.751	2.02E-06	0.000183095
42	CG31904	4637.723	-6.037	1.133	-5.328	9.94E-08	1.53E-05
43	CG14565	16.873	-6.026	1.572	-3.834	0.000126282	0.004840595
44	Cpr49Ae	4769.455	-6.014	0.985	-6.108	1.01E-09	3.13E-07
45	TwdlB	39.348	-5.964	1.412	-4.224	2.40E-05	0.00133743
46	Ccp84Aa	44.993	-5.947	1.198	-4.963	6.93E-07	7.46E-05
47	Or47a	147.679	-5.914	0.931	-6.350	2.16E-10	7.69E-08
48	CG16885	2322.837	-5.905	1.187	-4.975	6.51E-07	7.08E-05

49	Osi7	105.886	-5.866	1.326	-4.424	9.71E-06	0.000660712
50	CG11413	309.682	-5.848	1.022	-5.721	1.06E-08	2.37E-06
51	Cpr97Eb	756.403	-5.737	0.960	-5.977	2.28E-09	6.55E-07
52	CG34217	85.606	-5.622	1.125	-4.997	5.83E-07	6.46E-05
53	Zasp67	592.419	-5.610	1.030	-5.445	5.18E-08	9.15E-06
54	CG1368	242.569	-5.504	0.940	-5.854	4.80E-09	1.17E-06
55	CG15080	288.145	-5.432	1.020	-5.327	9.97E-08	1.53E-05
56	CG14573	2.878	-5.380	1.315	-4.091	4.29E-05	0.002050663
57	CG4962	716.023	-5.349	0.975	-5.488	4.06E-08	7.33E-06
58	CG16884	2158.788	-5.333	1.200	-4.444	8.82E-06	0.000610864
59	CG34461	18.876	-5.310	1.172	-4.530	5.90E-06	0.000439614
60	St2	3.637	-5.263	1.286	-4.092	4.29E-05	0.002050663
61	Cpr50Cb	69.627	-5.234	1.026	-5.101	3.39E-07	4.24E-05
62	kkv	543.646	-5.137	0.876	-5.861	4.60E-09	1.15E-06
63	CG2650	488.299	-5.128	1.099	-4.665	3.08E-06	0.000261898
64	CG15212	14.328	-4.925	1.228	-4.009	6.10E-05	0.002645635
65	CG10183	4.856	-4.920	1.249	-3.940	8.13E-05	0.003360287
66	TwdlF	28.056	-4.918	1.215	-4.048	5.16E-05	0.002354162
67	CG13643	101.581	-4.874	0.881	-5.532	3.16E-08	6.05E-06
68	CR44492	19.817	-4.854	1.160	-4.183	2.88E-05	0.001553568
69	CR45664	16.979	-4.826	0.860	-5.612	2.00E-08	4.06E-06
70	Lsp1gamma	176.325	-4.780	1.114	-4.289	1.79E-05	0.0010704
71	Obp83g	40.984	-4.768	0.947	-5.033	4.83E-07	5.66E-05
72	Lcp65Ag3	90.204	-4.681	1.163	-4.026	5.68E-05	0.002511726
73	obst-A	641.322	-4.659	0.858	-5.432	5.57E-08	9.68E-06
74	CG13026	115.197	-4.640	0.912	-5.086	3.65E-07	4.54E-05
75	CG13063	48.740	-4.605	0.957	-4.813	1.49E-06	0.000141809
76	CG17147	350.700	-4.582	0.557	-8.221	2.02E-16	5.53E-13
77	l(3)mbn	41.275	-4.570	1.059	-4.315	1.59E-05	0.000989808
78	CR44769	3.962	-4.561	1.106	-4.122	3.75E-05	0.001865199
79	CG42792	35.315	-4.551	1.089	-4.180	2.91E-05	0.001560861
80	Lcp65Ag1	86.790	-4.545	1.179	-3.856	0.000115451	0.004488351
81	Cht7	344.186	-4.517	0.894	-5.052	4.37E-07	5.19E-05
82	zye	420.766	-4.484	0.954	-4.698	2.63E-06	0.000231723
83	CG13044	181.240	-4.469	1.047	-4.268	1.98E-05	0.001157994
84	prc	198.315	-4.456	0.849	-5.247	1.55E-07	2.15E-05
85	Cda4	251.446	-4.365	0.899	-4.855	1.21E-06	0.000117049
86	y	51.505	-4.327	1.156	-3.742	0.000182915	0.00626495
87	verm	2682.579	-4.302	0.843	-5.104	3.32E-07	4.19E-05
88	Scp1	30418.593	-4.207	0.638	-6.590	4.40E-11	2.26E-08
89	Muc91C	10.169	-4.143	1.125	-3.683	0.000230214	0.007538711
90	CG42323	49.596	-4.114	0.903	-4.554	5.25E-06	0.00039709
91	Cpr11A	31.209	-4.082	0.892	-4.576	4.75E-06	0.000365664

92	Ccp84Ag	50.686	-4.057	0.725	-5.593	2.23E-08	4.36E-06
93	CG13071	28.605	-3.980	0.956	-4.163	3.14E-05	0.001665111
94	Cpr92A	80.296	-3.963	1.097	-3.613	0.000302406	0.009256119
95	CG15023	9.033	-3.951	0.779	-5.072	3.93E-07	4.82E-05
96	Lcp65Ag2	91.004	-3.908	1.011	-3.864	0.000111628	0.004402344
97	CR44603	19.095	-3.888	0.898	-4.331	1.49E-05	0.000938859
98	CG16786	224.357	-3.861	0.731	-5.284	1.26E-07	1.90E-05
99	Act79B	31094.285	-3.850	0.739	-5.208	1.91E-07	2.57E-05
100	CG43218	123.374	-3.847	0.586	-6.566	5.15E-11	2.42E-08
101	CG13606	466.501	-3.841	0.785	-4.893	9.95E-07	9.90E-05
102	CG15373	74.538	-3.791	0.731	-5.189	2.11E-07	2.79E-05
103	mir-4973	6.634	-3.783	0.910	-4.157	3.23E-05	0.001679901
104	lox2	148.910	-3.768	0.583	-6.458	1.06E-10	4.25E-08
105	CG8483	147.560	-3.686	0.856	-4.305	1.67E-05	0.001019399
106	CG13183	57.838	-3.685	0.744	-4.953	7.32E-07	7.74E-05
107	CG7896	134.942	-3.675	0.743	-4.946	7.57E-07	7.91E-05
108	Gasp	1688.673	-3.655	0.792	-4.613	3.97E-06	0.000317845
109	CG34276	23.307	-3.653	0.793	-4.605	4.12E-06	0.000323638
110	CG4000	5505.088	-3.584	0.680	-5.268	1.38E-07	1.96E-05
111	CG5873	69.309	-3.546	0.974	-3.641	0.000271589	0.008519467
112	CG9782	359.620	-3.520	0.766	-4.597	4.28E-06	0.000334569
113	Cht5	476.292	-3.507	0.914	-3.837	0.000124732	0.004792413
114	CG9090	10730.172	-3.445	0.638	-5.401	6.62E-08	1.11E-05
115	serp	1468.231	-3.442	0.795	-4.330	1.49E-05	0.000938859
116	CR45024	468.621	-3.440	0.685	-5.025	5.04E-07	5.83E-05
117	CG14752	55.303	-3.426	0.760	-4.506	6.60E-06	0.000481574
118	CG6739	74.636	-3.394	0.780	-4.352	1.35E-05	0.000873651
119	e	557.440	-3.296	0.803	-4.106	4.02E-05	0.001975826
120	Cht6	562.283	-3.283	0.841	-3.903	9.51E-05	0.003870613
121	Cpr76Bd	472.647	-3.261	0.747	-4.366	1.26E-05	0.000826826
122	CG5391	8.794	-3.254	0.865	-3.762	0.00016868	0.005925833
123	GstS1	31880.113	-3.165	0.696	-4.551	5.35E-06	0.000402716
124	CG34172	3630.576	-3.119	0.645	-4.838	1.31E-06	0.000126726
125	Osi9	33.401	-3.112	0.527	-5.906	3.51E-09	9.13E-07
126	CG15213	156.607	-3.092	0.514	-6.018	1.77E-09	5.27E-07
127	Peritrophin-A	196.049	-3.084	0.764	-4.034	5.48E-05	0.00245716
128	TpnC41C	4218.791	-3.083	0.574	-5.372	7.78E-08	1.26E-05
129	CG11345	12.800	-3.030	0.606	-4.999	5.76E-07	6.43E-05
130	obst-B	360.499	-3.026	0.755	-4.006	6.17E-05	0.002670033
131	CG15597	26.856	-2.998	0.608	-4.934	8.07E-07	8.38E-05
132	CG31775	964.355	-2.954	0.817	-3.616	0.000298646	0.009192464
133	CG4702	29.174	-2.947	0.766	-3.845	0.000120535	0.004642001
134	CG34038	5.059	-2.925	0.798	-3.665	0.000247549	0.007932192

135	Mlc2	86950.802	-2.907	0.630	-4.618	3.87E-06	0.000313294
136	CtrlB	1275.470	-2.903	0.572	-5.075	3.87E-07	4.77E-05
137	Mlc1	36333.867	-2.899	0.630	-4.605	4.12E-06	0.000323638
138	CG42586	1219.281	-2.896	0.775	-3.739	0.000185016	0.006310551
139	CG14566	17.394	-2.841	0.730	-3.891	9.98E-05	0.00401181
140	l(2)34Fc	2312.409	-2.837	0.700	-4.052	5.08E-05	0.002333778
141	CG13023	19.797	-2.827	0.717	-3.942	8.09E-05	0.003359969
142	CG13067	405.539	-2.816	0.605	-4.656	3.22E-06	0.000268551
143	CG13305	21.272	-2.807	0.524	-5.354	8.62E-08	1.37E-05
144	TwdIV	16.062	-2.802	0.746	-3.756	0.000172632	0.005987731
145	Strn-Mlck	19126.098	-2.780	0.633	-4.391	1.13E-05	0.000752572
146	CR44850	883.500	-2.774	0.689	-4.026	5.67E-05	0.002511726
147	CG4835	256.202	-2.759	0.560	-4.929	8.25E-07	8.46E-05
148	Mhc	163894.787	-2.751	0.638	-4.315	1.60E-05	0.000990169
149	CG4374	52.744	-2.749	0.616	-4.465	8.00E-06	0.000560688
150	CG17974	14.934	-2.701	0.593	-4.555	5.23E-06	0.00039709
151	CG17777	106.109	-2.696	0.561	-4.805	1.55E-06	0.000146156
152	CG7906	6.971	-2.694	0.643	-4.187	2.82E-05	0.001531691
153	retinin	1445.162	-2.689	0.647	-4.158	3.22E-05	0.001679901
154	CG8501	60.566	-2.679	0.631	-4.245	2.18E-05	0.001256154
155	CG15021	1251.376	-2.672	0.672	-3.979	6.91E-05	0.002936231
156	CG18367	43.333	-2.671	0.493	-5.420	5.95E-08	1.01E-05
157	Cpr49Ag	47.318	-2.670	0.451	-5.913	3.35E-09	9.01E-07
158	Cpr49Ab	1921.366	-2.619	0.709	-3.696	0.00021877	0.007221603
159	CG12009	42.288	-2.598	0.704	-3.690	0.000224001	0.007364653
160	CG13678	16.238	-2.568	0.609	-4.215	2.49E-05	0.00137546
161	CG12672	35.799	-2.564	0.383	-6.692	2.20E-11	1.43E-08
162	CG6118	30.264	-2.541	0.699	-3.634	0.000279454	0.008683185
163	mag	3776.051	-2.475	0.383	-6.458	1.06E-10	4.25E-08
164	CG15515	152.579	-2.440	0.626	-3.899	9.68E-05	0.003911139
165	ft	336.722	-2.426	0.425	-5.705	1.16E-08	2.54E-06
166	CG33639	157.631	-2.423	0.406	-5.961	2.50E-09	6.96E-07
167	Unc-89	10603.089	-2.405	0.561	-4.284	1.84E-05	0.001093262
168	CR43988	14.859	-2.397	0.663	-3.617	0.000298031	0.009190773
169	CG34375	52.581	-2.383	0.636	-3.749	0.000177832	0.006129226
170	CG7714	27.688	-2.369	0.517	-4.584	4.57E-06	0.000355105
171	CG40198	272.290	-2.360	0.605	-3.903	9.51E-05	0.003870613
172	Npc2d	689.308	-2.305	0.536	-4.298	1.73E-05	0.001049399
173	Hsp67Bc	141.742	-2.304	0.597	-3.859	0.000113685	0.004440295
174	CG15434	243.469	-2.300	0.405	-5.674	1.40E-08	2.90E-06
175	fj	88.475	-2.299	0.604	-3.804	0.000142279	0.005245468
176	ple	3060.717	-2.284	0.636	-3.592	0.000328	0.009801768
177	CG34382	41.365	-2.255	0.620	-3.640	0.000272306	0.008525664

178	snmRNA:419	37.831	-2.235	0.539	-4.146	3.38E-05	0.001730928
179	CG12105	381.405	-2.225	0.526	-4.234	2.30E-05	0.001294219
180	Tm2	34932.786	-2.224	0.501	-4.439	9.04E-06	0.000623418
181	Ca-P60A	59765.827	-2.211	0.336	-6.571	5.00E-11	2.41E-08
182	CG6472	70.559	-2.195	0.416	-5.278	1.31E-07	1.92E-05
183	Npc2c	30.333	-2.185	0.552	-3.957	7.59E-05	0.003184035
184	Cpr62Bb	353.127	-2.185	0.533	-4.101	4.12E-05	0.001994881
185	Cda5	1433.993	-2.167	0.596	-3.637	0.000275618	0.008596561
186	CG9297	19094.220	-2.160	0.371	-5.825	5.70E-09	1.36E-06
187	CG14625	24.515	-2.131	0.580	-3.674	0.000238892	0.00774557
188	bt	31227.463	-2.113	0.495	-4.268	1.97E-05	0.001157994
189	CR44654	8.272	-2.099	0.570	-3.683	0.000230094	0.007538711
190	Prm	30453.647	-2.097	0.514	-4.077	4.56E-05	0.002151977
191	CG4115	241.523	-2.095	0.488	-4.294	1.75E-05	0.001060781
192	CR45591	131.166	-2.089	0.554	-3.768	0.000164736	0.005837278
193	CG14742	336.441	-2.039	0.504	-4.045	5.24E-05	0.002375237
194	kdn	24995.195	-2.022	0.489	-4.136	3.53E-05	0.001783555
195	Cpr11B	48.243	-2.019	0.474	-4.262	2.03E-05	0.001183382
196	CG32037	46.548	-2.013	0.501	-4.020	5.81E-05	0.00255042
197	CG17211	72.824	-2.004	0.465	-4.313	1.61E-05	0.000994802
198	CG13856	64.036	-1.982	0.449	-4.418	9.96E-06	0.00067494
199	CG32814	111.336	-1.975	0.498	-3.970	7.20E-05	0.003047654
200	CG15615	21.278	-1.971	0.443	-4.452	8.50E-06	0.000590979
201	CG42255	169.786	-1.962	0.483	-4.063	4.84E-05	0.002257092
202	CG14246	326.393	-1.961	0.411	-4.766	1.88E-06	0.000173162
203	ds	485.608	-1.929	0.493	-3.916	9.02E-05	0.00369022
204	GstD7	38.976	-1.897	0.399	-4.756	1.98E-06	0.000180102
205	CG45218	2061.974	-1.879	0.487	-3.859	0.000113708	0.004440295
206	Abl	9487.098	-1.872	0.432	-4.331	1.48E-05	0.000938859
207	CG8927	318.518	-1.866	0.519	-3.596	0.00032324	0.009699442
208	CG9192	63.313	-1.866	0.398	-4.687	2.78E-06	0.000242305
209	CG44142	856.529	-1.859	0.406	-4.579	4.66E-06	0.000360793
210	Gpo-1	6669.610	-1.858	0.508	-3.655	0.000256709	0.008146162
211	CG9642	13.492	-1.842	0.477	-3.859	0.000113944	0.004440295
212	Sh	2284.912	-1.840	0.371	-4.958	7.14E-07	7.60E-05
213	mthl13	39.366	-1.836	0.480	-3.824	0.00013144	0.00499166
214	dao	230.481	-1.831	0.346	-5.287	1.24E-07	1.89E-05
215	CG9095	160.166	-1.820	0.479	-3.803	0.000143136	0.005265232
216	MtmB	1153.489	-1.814	0.467	-3.886	0.000101746	0.004061418
217	CG12483	82.782	-1.813	0.437	-4.150	3.33E-05	0.001717579
218	mir-4982	13.071	-1.795	0.426	-4.214	2.51E-05	0.00137546
219	Act87E	22773.479	-1.791	0.396	-4.517	6.26E-06	0.000462809
220	Tm1	46829.064	-1.778	0.475	-3.744	0.000181059	0.006214345

221	RunxB	18.357	-1.769	0.455	-3.888	0.000101204	0.004049659
222	CG11162	87.267	-1.760	0.361	-4.876	1.08E-06	0.000106901
223	RyR	7231.416	-1.745	0.453	-3.854	0.000116341	0.004512283
224	CG2022	269.237	-1.740	0.448	-3.888	0.000100964	0.004049659
225	Obp28a	238.483	-1.722	0.323	-5.334	9.62E-08	1.50E-05
226	CG34155	240.827	-1.714	0.475	-3.607	0.000309728	0.009409998
227	CG11321	2825.057	-1.708	0.424	-4.026	5.68E-05	0.002511726
228	Cpr47Ee	134.351	-1.690	0.399	-4.238	2.26E-05	0.001289472
229	pncr004:X	53.827	-1.680	0.412	-4.073	4.64E-05	0.002180688
230	CG14854	63.351	-1.667	0.316	-5.281	1.29E-07	1.92E-05
231	CG1537	26.329	-1.664	0.407	-4.090	4.31E-05	0.002050663
232	tipE	298.186	-1.662	0.382	-4.346	1.38E-05	0.000893755
233	b	732.964	-1.659	0.406	-4.089	4.34E-05	0.002057179
234	CG7631	221.213	-1.657	0.327	-5.066	4.06E-07	4.93E-05
235	CG6329	974.041	-1.647	0.305	-5.395	6.85E-08	1.14E-05
236	CG1304	544.845	-1.641	0.200	-8.187	2.67E-16	6.17E-13
237	Cpr65Au	1781.923	-1.639	0.348	-4.712	2.46E-06	0.000218021
238	CR44997	19.182	-1.631	0.437	-3.731	0.000190877	0.006483488
239	CG9682	2223.606	-1.613	0.381	-4.232	2.31E-05	0.001295621
240	CG1732	608.954	-1.612	0.427	-3.772	0.000162143	0.00577033
241	Spn31A	156.946	-1.612	0.312	-5.162	2.44E-07	3.17E-05
242	CR45226	30.911	-1.604	0.326	-4.917	8.81E-07	8.98E-05
243	snoRNA:Me18S-A1061	22.478	-1.579	0.360	-4.385	1.16E-05	0.000770709
244	CG14298	96.566	-1.567	0.387	-4.049	5.14E-05	0.002353294
245	Cyt-c-p	26204.624	-1.562	0.380	-4.116	3.86E-05	0.001905433
246	salm	425.846	-1.541	0.359	-4.291	1.78E-05	0.001069387
247	CG9468	6770.701	-1.541	0.406	-3.799	0.000145439	0.005311543
248	CG3713	150.634	-1.540	0.420	-3.666	0.000246586	0.007932192
249	CG18136	126.055	-1.510	0.375	-4.024	5.72E-05	0.002517687
250	Ugt86Dg	48.350	-1.507	0.368	-4.094	4.24E-05	0.002042182
251	CG17374	6012.289	-1.504	0.364	-4.131	3.61E-05	0.001805756
252	Actn	13137.543	-1.493	0.408	-3.663	0.000249658	0.007965439
253	snoRNA:Or-CD4	24.263	-1.491	0.363	-4.104	4.06E-05	0.001977334
254	CG10581	135.951	-1.484	0.403	-3.682	0.000231589	0.007568627
255	CG32407	787.724	-1.483	0.331	-4.477	7.58E-06	0.000540577
256	tmod	6029.938	-1.480	0.356	-4.162	3.15E-05	0.001666046
257	para	2587.828	-1.472	0.378	-3.896	9.77E-05	0.003937607
258	CG8628	3735.722	-1.470	0.293	-5.020	5.18E-07	5.94E-05
259	CG42319	1662.157	-1.469	0.300	-4.895	9.84E-07	9.84E-05
260	Gpdh	18741.562	-1.465	0.363	-4.031	5.55E-05	0.002480623
261	Mical	10082.424	-1.458	0.346	-4.215	2.50E-05	0.00137546
262	haf	470.574	-1.452	0.397	-3.660	0.000252488	0.008027744

263	Hsc70-1	2713.106	-1.451	0.402	-3.608	0.000309147	0.009409783
264	Dop2R	834.297	-1.430	0.386	-3.706	0.000210367	0.006972279
265	CG14459	57.593	-1.417	0.371	-3.821	0.000132859	0.005007647
266	CG4461	1655.760	-1.405	0.175	-8.037	9.22E-16	1.68E-12
267	CG9486	73.162	-1.391	0.321	-4.333	1.47E-05	0.000938859
268	TM4SF	786.462	-1.342	0.311	-4.317	1.58E-05	0.000986763
269	CR44986	2139.431	-1.342	0.373	-3.600	0.000317929	0.009605776
270	nrm	1370.728	-1.328	0.349	-3.801	0.000143896	0.005280574
271	pHCl	1205.234	-1.327	0.369	-3.596	0.000323394	0.009699442
272	CG42337	268.494	-1.320	0.356	-3.711	0.000206487	0.006885426
273	CG8665	700.113	-1.318	0.358	-3.680	0.000233381	0.007612016
274	CG6439	9964.128	-1.318	0.347	-3.792	0.000149443	0.005436264
275	CG1136	616.144	-1.306	0.347	-3.761	0.000169063	0.005926586
276	CG18536	125.904	-1.299	0.290	-4.482	7.39E-06	0.000529138
277	Frq2	679.405	-1.294	0.290	-4.460	8.21E-06	0.000573173
278	CG5999	178.952	-1.291	0.279	-4.633	3.61E-06	0.000295125
279	luna	835.944	-1.284	0.319	-4.028	5.62E-05	0.002506513
280	danr	55.690	-1.273	0.307	-4.142	3.45E-05	0.001745681
281	MsR2	122.995	-1.269	0.321	-3.951	7.79E-05	0.003259936
282	CG14482	8278.558	-1.239	0.303	-4.087	4.38E-05	0.00206998
283	nrv3	4476.249	-1.236	0.310	-3.990	6.60E-05	0.002810344
284	Zasp52	12960.715	-1.225	0.303	-4.039	5.37E-05	0.002412261
285	CG3841	1025.673	-1.218	0.297	-4.105	4.04E-05	0.001977334
286	Fhos	4016.235	-1.201	0.259	-4.644	3.42E-06	0.000281596
287	CG13003	478.513	-1.191	0.315	-3.777	0.000158707	0.00566031
288	CG7580	19980.190	-1.189	0.194	-6.136	8.48E-10	2.68E-07
289	CR45712	199.518	-1.186	0.315	-3.763	0.000167724	0.005904887
290	tutl	1215.467	-1.180	0.317	-3.726	0.000194564	0.006567934
291	CG40472	4837.485	-1.174	0.293	-4.013	6.00E-05	0.002611899
292	antdh	272.432	-1.158	0.308	-3.760	0.000169773	0.005935025
293	CG43149	61.030	-1.140	0.268	-4.255	2.09E-05	0.001205944
294	CG11876	11223.836	-1.140	0.237	-4.811	1.50E-06	0.000142095
295	CG33510	33.672	-1.130	0.309	-3.653	0.00025946	0.008201742
296	CG1674	4132.038	-1.125	0.285	-3.945	7.97E-05	0.003325293
297	CG42346	315.392	-1.122	0.297	-3.782	0.00015583	0.005608867
298	CG3560	10390.486	-1.121	0.296	-3.786	0.000153155	0.005546724
299	CG7781	933.660	-1.119	0.294	-3.806	0.000141172	0.005245468
300	udd	646.532	-1.117	0.234	-4.767	1.87E-06	0.000173162
301	CG33296	109.552	-1.111	0.306	-3.633	0.000280078	0.008686137
302	ATPsyn-Cf6	22331.333	-1.096	0.301	-3.642	0.000270346	0.00849673
303	CG4692	12668.329	-1.091	0.260	-4.198	2.70E-05	0.001475859
304	CG6463	1981.578	-1.086	0.267	-4.068	4.73E-05	0.002218181
305	CR43957	52.352	-1.086	0.262	-4.142	3.44E-05	0.001745681

306	CG18107	814.713	-1.085	0.240	-4.515	6.32E-06	0.000465068
307	mir-929	305.943	-1.077	0.299	-3.601	0.000317479	0.009605776
308	CoVb	9675.183	-1.075	0.269	-4.002	6.27E-05	0.002706187
309	CG32230	12291.814	-1.074	0.204	-5.273	1.34E-07	1.95E-05
310	Neb-cGP	10111.835	-1.060	0.258	-4.109	3.98E-05	0.001961529
311	CG12119	671.301	-1.058	0.254	-4.173	3.01E-05	0.001607399
312	CG9034	2585.079	-1.056	0.285	-3.704	0.000212068	0.007014476
313	CG40002	6445.759	-1.050	0.261	-4.018	5.87E-05	0.002569897
314	bi	269.895	-1.047	0.281	-3.724	0.00019635	0.006601049
315	CG3192	3975.664	-1.042	0.275	-3.791	0.000149948	0.005442564
316	CG5548	3355.738	-1.042	0.230	-4.527	5.98E-06	0.00044396
317	CG33521	3541.515	-1.039	0.260	-3.990	6.59E-05	0.002810344
318	Rh50	677.636	-1.039	0.252	-4.123	3.74E-05	0.001864918
319	CoVIII	7461.435	-1.037	0.271	-3.821	0.000133081	0.005007647
320	CG7630	13105.576	-1.031	0.234	-4.405	1.06E-05	0.000710009
321	mRpL27	1313.804	-1.022	0.185	-5.532	3.17E-08	6.05E-06
322	Pfk	6416.630	-1.018	0.267	-3.818	0.00013434	0.005031906
323	CG10320	10086.579	-1.012	0.233	-4.345	1.39E-05	0.000897111
324	CG6733	1194.402	-1.010	0.216	-4.664	3.10E-06	0.000262432
325	snoRNA:Me28S-G2703c	34.428	-0.997	0.261	-3.822	0.000132243	0.005007647
326	CG12859	1997.149	-0.992	0.244	-4.064	4.83E-05	0.00225581
327	CG14661	1926.116	-0.982	0.239	-4.103	4.07E-05	0.001977334
328	CG9306	5319.977	-0.982	0.258	-3.807	0.00014042	0.00523575
329	CheB38c	76.363	-0.980	0.269	-3.642	0.000270105	0.00849673
330	CG34439	3178.814	-0.976	0.214	-4.571	4.86E-06	0.000372874
331	CG3321	10906.747	-0.966	0.236	-4.090	4.31E-05	0.002050663
332	CheA7a	273.572	-0.949	0.248	-3.830	0.000128223	0.00489215
333	levy	11674.570	-0.937	0.251	-3.730	0.000191525	0.00649207
334	cype	9871.802	-0.928	0.253	-3.665	0.000247527	0.007932192
335	bnb	3647.168	-0.926	0.247	-3.746	0.000179404	0.006170455
336	CG15629	120.410	-0.918	0.214	-4.289	1.79E-05	0.0010704
337	CoVIIc	14295.508	-0.912	0.228	-3.994	6.49E-05	0.002783727
338	CG18853	1568.274	-0.904	0.176	-5.135	2.82E-07	3.61E-05
339	CoVa	13253.721	-0.886	0.202	-4.380	1.18E-05	0.000783706
340	CG3214	4054.794	-0.885	0.216	-4.099	4.15E-05	0.002003868
341	CG31323	128.041	-0.880	0.233	-3.780	0.00015695	0.00562211
342	CoIV	15422.205	-0.877	0.227	-3.863	0.000111979	0.004405572
343	CG6432	1232.400	-0.877	0.175	-5.016	5.28E-07	6.01E-05
344	snmRNA:359	265.589	-0.861	0.238	-3.613	0.000302168	0.009256119
345	l(2)06225	20016.603	-0.860	0.212	-4.055	5.01E-05	0.00231731
346	CG14606	194.131	-0.854	0.149	-5.729	1.01E-08	2.30E-06
347	CG7712	3230.884	-0.852	0.228	-3.736	0.000187277	0.006374421

348	CG5177	2622.150	-0.845	0.225	-3.750	0.000177031	0.006114467
349	CG15822	454.130	-0.842	0.224	-3.766	0.000166173	0.005862883
350	CG8012	1199.215	-0.842	0.219	-3.852	0.000117247	0.00453667
351	Zasp66	14150.688	-0.841	0.220	-3.819	0.000134098	0.005031906
352	Ant2	4506.151	-0.837	0.216	-3.881	0.000104038	0.004142816
353	CG10219	4011.205	-0.835	0.173	-4.821	1.43E-06	0.00013723
354	CG31446	367.644	-0.827	0.225	-3.669	0.000243266	0.007856349
355	CG44242	1315.064	-0.827	0.199	-4.159	3.20E-05	0.001679901
356	NP15.6	3000.800	-0.823	0.227	-3.620	0.000294781	0.009107675
357	CG1970	6029.785	-0.822	0.220	-3.740	0.00018371	0.006279069
358	Mlp84B	10468.050	-0.821	0.186	-4.407	1.05E-05	0.000707676
359	Prx5	5412.786	-0.819	0.141	-5.814	6.09E-09	1.43E-06
360	l(1)G0136	1129.327	-0.806	0.179	-4.493	7.02E-06	0.000505705
361	Prosalphal	9288.376	-0.805	0.187	-4.306	1.66E-05	0.001016007
362	CG3621	2967.121	-0.802	0.188	-4.260	2.04E-05	0.001188056
363	CG11617	195.320	-0.800	0.190	-4.216	2.49E-05	0.00137546
364	CG30382	9480.904	-0.797	0.193	-4.135	3.55E-05	0.001788484
365	CG17026	259.411	-0.787	0.182	-4.327	1.51E-05	0.000950196
366	mir-4967	86.893	-0.786	0.151	-5.203	1.96E-07	2.61E-05
367	Mf	46470.056	-0.781	0.169	-4.605	4.12E-06	0.000323638
368	CoVIb	17934.595	-0.773	0.211	-3.670	0.000242142	0.007835468
369	l(2)03659	93.263	-0.769	0.162	-4.756	1.97E-06	0.000180102
370	Fili	126.803	-0.764	0.208	-3.666	0.00024682	0.007932192
371	CG5023	2279.186	-0.756	0.209	-3.611	0.000304835	0.009313067
372	Argk	83791.819	-0.724	0.192	-3.767	0.000165406	0.005848375
373	Cralbp	162.549	-0.712	0.176	-4.043	5.28E-05	0.002381049
374	kcc	4123.316	-0.703	0.195	-3.610	0.000305823	0.009325891
375	HmgZ	4549.367	-0.693	0.126	-5.516	3.46E-08	6.45E-06
376	CG10550	1486.181	-0.677	0.162	-4.181	2.91E-05	0.001560861
377	CG17109	646.295	-0.674	0.168	-4.017	5.89E-05	0.002571726
378	CG17027	777.825	-0.667	0.185	-3.600	0.000318674	0.009610585
379	CG7231	969.325	-0.652	0.180	-3.614	0.000301538	0.009256119
380	CG30054	397.069	-0.638	0.177	-3.604	0.000313701	0.00951308
381	CG9249	613.615	-0.630	0.145	-4.357	1.32E-05	0.000859497
382	CG4848	1272.899	-0.610	0.160	-3.821	0.000132678	0.005007647
383	CG17029	1646.513	-0.599	0.158	-3.781	0.000155897	0.005608867
384	CG14431	181.687	-0.585	0.157	-3.724	0.000195859	0.006598087
385	CG7215	2466.968	-0.582	0.137	-4.236	2.28E-05	0.001294219
386	CG32500	1283.226	-0.520	0.138	-3.769	0.000163859	0.005818771
387	slmo	7194.270	-0.516	0.140	-3.679	0.000234489	0.00763299
388	CG33502	6281.878	-0.482	0.133	-3.632	0.000281211	0.008704796
389	CG34179	3718.006	-0.478	0.126	-3.805	0.000141626	0.005245468
390	CG31812	418.567	-0.463	0.122	-3.777	0.000158467	0.00566031

391	AMPdeam	5306.512	-0.426	0.095	-4.474	7.67E-06	0.000544836
392	P5CDh1	5050.834	-0.415	0.103	-4.047	5.19E-05	0.002360572
393	CaMKII	4796.098	-0.407	0.107	-3.801	0.000144197	0.005280574
394	CG9603	10340.614	-0.384	0.090	-4.257	2.07E-05	0.00119971
395	CG8993	1557.517	-0.358	0.089	-4.043	5.28E-05	0.002381049
396	tacc	6664.034	-0.300	0.049	-6.184	6.26E-10	2.14E-07
397	PRL-1	4967.644	-0.268	0.064	-4.214	2.51E-05	0.00137546

INT (compared with NINT)

	Gene symbol	baseMean	log2FoldChange	lfcSE	stat	Pvalue	Padj
1	sha	1929.002	-7.693	1.327	-5.798	6.72E-09	2.16E-05
2	Or47b	301.666	-7.327	1.513	-4.842	1.29E-06	0.001371225
3	Obp47b	149.550	-6.828	1.577	-4.330	1.49E-05	0.007060236
4	nompA	1136.894	-4.635	1.013	-4.575	4.75E-06	0.002966214
5	CG7741	2210.587	-3.318	0.761	-4.357	1.32E-05	0.006617489
6	CR44192	618.494	-1.669	0.341	-4.894	9.90E-07	0.001224877
7	CG9547	716.607	-0.570	0.119	-4.793	1.64E-06	0.001371225
8	spict	771.656	-0.507	0.104	-4.852	1.22E-06	0.001371225
9	yip2	3603.651	-0.405	0.093	-4.343	1.40E-05	0.006848324
10	Nsf2	2055.828	-0.344	0.078	-4.380	1.19E-05	0.006172458

70

71 Supplementary Table S7. The list of the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway

72 INT (compared with F₀)

ID	Description	setSize	enrichmentScore	NES	pvalue	p.adjust	qvalues	rank	leading_ edge	core_enrichment
dme01200	Carbon metabolism	93	-0.560521896	-1.877 17765 5	0.0001	0.00651 3694	0.005713 766	3658	tags= 65 %, list=3 0%, signal=45%	42626/34414/39986/34474/35886/34554/44291/42832/32292/39899/326220/41869/32974/41360/246599/32013/33351/39085/45875/3772542/33475/41269/31185/39988/3772692/43102/42620/42185/40409/47173/40445/33459/41324/43191/317974/117364/35728/46246/37900/34198/38358/39469/43582/33461/31407/41787/39945/317829/43447/39470/40012/36839/36060/42621/41253/37541/41468/36904/3771779/31579
dme03008	Ribosome biogenesis in eukaryotes	74	-0.546414784	-1.767 74136 1	0.0001	0.00651 3694	0.005713 766	196	tags= 18 %, list=2 %, signal=18%	2768873/2768872/2768902/2768897/2768904/2768873/2768905/7354447/2768899/2768898/117463/2768899/2768873/2768873
dme01230	Biosynthesis of amino acids	52	-0.618350843	-1.883 82679 3	0.0001	0.00651 3694	0.005713 766	3398	tags= 69 %, list=2 8%, signal=50%	34554/44291/42732/32292/42729/39878/246599/41274/33351/39085/33475/38871/41269/43102/42620/40409/33459/42730/35728/46246/37900/42728/43582/33461/41787/39945/317829/43447/40012/42783/36060/42731/42621/41468/36904/31579
dme04137	Mitophagy - animal	46	-0.613791737	-1.832 63083 6	0.0004	0.01474 0917	0.012930 629	196	tags= 30 %, list=2 %, signal=30%	2768873/2768872/33797/2768902/2768897/2768904/2768873/2768905/7354447/2768899/2768898/117463/2768899/2768873/2768873
dme03010	Ribosome	132	0.448846615	1.7437 71078	0.0008	0.02088 6076	0.018321 119	3314	tags= 58 %, list=2 7%, signal=43%	50381/36570/38397/31009/42464/31483/41200/36851/45329/31700/43103/37628/31106/35988/34412/3355144/43169/32635/40451/43723/31897/38794/34625/44783/39088/36321/35453/31613/34329/32953/36985/43573/39480/44150/34526/39484/33629/43594/42470/49425/34352/34420/40091/3354918/34098/36855/43349/42061/40654/33487/40060/37430/44059/37589/33654/35098/41120/31228/42761/41372/40687/43532/31588/41807/38983/32700/40980/37292/33214/36576/251466/44326/34149/41347/37235/38208/3355124
dme00010	Glycolysis / Gluconeogenesis	42	-0.603670663	-1.778 57883 2	0.0010	0.02302 6316	0.020198 523	2642	tags= 57 %, list=2 2%, signal=45%	33351/45875/33475/39988/42620/34779/40409/33459/32345/43191/117364/35728/46246/43582/36510/261603/33461/31407/41787/39945/43447/36060/42621/36904

dme00620	Pyruvate metabolism	34	-0.636442254	-1.800662366	0.0014	0.025808133	0.022638714	2762	tags=59%, list=23%, signal=46%	49997/3772542/33475/39988/3772692/42620/42185/40409/47173/5740441/36556/39469/36510/31407/41787/39945/39470/36839/42621/31830
dme04310	Wnt signaling pathway	93	-0.492154573	-1.648216732	0.0018	0.029920491	0.026246045	1533	tags=23%, list=13%, signal=20%	37300/37909/35065/12798588/37763/32188/34819/2768873/42574/2768872/2768902/2768897/2768904/2768873/2768905/7354447/2768899/2768898/117463/2768899/2768873/2768873
dme04140	Autophagy - animal	93	0.456765579	1.68189576	0.0032	0.046593717	0.040871681	2251	tags=26%, list=19%, signal=21%	326175/326174/34493/326263/34494/42094/33330/3354888/42692/31666/42096/45268/39150/40201/42095/318725/43991/37733/41957/35793/33283/42358/40653/40278
dme00051	Fructose and mannose metabolism	24	-0.6352817	-1.674137086	0.0075	0.098584098	0.086477279	2700	tags=62%, list=22%, signal=49%	35586/38463/40204/45875/39280/40203/38462/39305/40836/43191/117364/43582/19988923/39279/36060
dme01200	Carbon metabolism	93	-0.560521896	-1.877177655	0.0001	0.006513694	0.005713766	3658	tags=65%, list=30%, signal=45%	42626/34414/39986/34474/35886/34554/44291/42832/32292/39899/326220/41869/32974/41360/246599/32013/33351/39085/45875/3772542/33475/41269/31185/39988/3772692/43102/42620/42185/40409/47173/40445/33459/41324/43191/317974/117364/35728/46246/37900/34198/38358/39469/43582/33461/31407/41787/39945/317829/43447/39470/40012/36839/36060/42621/41253/37541/41468/36904/3771779/31579

73 NINT (compared with F₀)

ID	Description	setSize	enrichmentScore	NES	pvalue	p.adjust	qvalues	rank	leading_edge	core_enrichment
dme03430	Mismatch repair	17	-0.739592638	-2.194604841	0.000388802	0.013877119	0.011596789	2036	tags=94%, list=17%, signal=78%	34423/38492/40607/37290/40972/35364/32113/34842/34550/32763/35119/34892/36705/39746/35796/39654
dme03440	Homologous recombination	22	-0.743128459	-2.347771274	0.000426621	0.013877119	0.011596789	2500	tags=91%, list=21%, signal=72%	41839/44259/31044/41366/40972/35364/32113/41746/31565/43577/33507/34892/34565/39746/35236/48309/318579/37564/36136/35937
dme03460	Fanconi anemia pathway	23	-0.774869364	-2.492096398	0.000429553	0.013877119	0.011596789	2441	tags=96%, list=20%, signal=77%	31044/35895/41366/40972/35364/36654/40965/32113/41231/38079/31565/43577/40438/31373/36705/35236/2768674/35796/318579/32608/36136/36199

dme03030	DNA replication	30	-0.736465095	-2.538225161	0.000494805	0.013877119	0.011596789	3041	tags=93%, list=25%, signal=70%	34423/37560/246459/38492/3772329/40607/37290/38942/31603/40972/35364/32113/34550/32763/36887/34892/35679/42553/39746/40973/41296/31449/39014/31934/44915/33213/43278/32323
dme03420	Nucleotide excision repair	33	-0.619091504	-2.171628131	0.000529661	0.013877119	0.011596789	3108	tags=79%, list=26%, signal=59%	35780/34423/37560/40429/36130/38492/39688/31441/3772329/31357/36598/40607/37290/40972/35364/36654/32113/41611/3772069/34550/32763/33294/34892/31373/39746/37414
dme04624	Toll and Imd signaling pathway	70	-0.613077608	-2.519798733	0.000925069	0.020197348	0.016878459	994	tags=29%, list=8%, signal=27%	43283/39020/42253/41087/42791/35862/43256/43222/38419/2768679/36047/50126/32099/38858/43596/43598/39870/43599/39869/38408/37184
dme03430	Mismatch repair	17	-0.739592638	-2.194604841	0.000388802	0.013877119	0.011596789	2036	tags=94%, list=17%, signal=78%	34423/38492/40607/37290/40972/35364/32113/34842/34550/32763/35119/34892/36705/39746/35796/39654
dme03440	Homologous recombination	22	-0.743128459	-2.347771274	0.000426621	0.013877119	0.011596789	2500	tags=91%, list=21%, signal=72%	41839/44259/31044/41366/40972/35364/32113/41746/31565/43577/33507/34892/34565/39746/35236/48309/318579/37564/36136/35937
dme03460	Fanconi anemia pathway	23	-0.774869364	-2.492096398	0.000429553	0.013877119	0.011596789	2441	tags=96%, list=20%, signal=77%	31044/35895/41366/40972/35364/36654/40965/32113/41231/38079/31565/43577/40438/31373/36705/35236/2768674/35796/318579/32608/36136/36199

74 INT (compared with NINT)

ID	Description	setSize	enrichmentScore	NES	pvalue	p.adjust	qvalues	rank	leading_edge	core_enrichment
dme03430	Mismatch repair	17	-0.739592638	-2.194604841	0.000388802	0.013877119	0.011596789	2036	tags=94%, list=17%, signal=78%	34423/38492/40607/37290/40972/35364/32113/34842/34550/32763/35119/34892/36705/39746/35796/39654
dme03440	Homologous recombination	22	-0.743128459	-2.347771274	0.000426621	0.013877119	0.011596789	2500	tags=91%, list=21%, signal=72%	41839/44259/31044/41366/40972/35364/32113/41746/31565/43577/33507/34892/34565/39746/35236/48309/318579/37564/36136/35937
dme03460	Fanconi anemia	23	-0.774869364	-2.492096398	0.000429553	0.013877119	0.011596789	2441	tags=96%, list=20%, signal=77%	31044/35895/41366/40972/35364/36654/40965/32113/41231/38079/31565/43577/40438/31373/36705/35236/2768674/35796/318579/32608/36136/36199

	pathway									
dme03030	DNA replication	30	-0.736465095	-2.538225161	0.000494805	0.013877119	0.011596789	3041	tags=93%, list=25%, signal=70%	34423/37560/246459/38492/3772329/40607/37290/38942/31603/40972/35364/32113/34550/32763/36887/34892/35679/42553/39746/40973/41296/31449/39014/31934/44915/33213/43278/32323
dme03420	Nucleotide excision repair	33	-0.619091504	-2.171628131	0.000529661	0.013877119	0.011596789	3108	tags=79%, list=26%, signal=59%	35780/34423/37560/40429/36130/38492/39688/31441/3772329/31357/36598/40607/37290/40972/35364/36654/32113/41611/3772069/34550/32763/33294/34892/31373/39746/37414
dme04624	Toll and Imd signaling pathway	70	-0.613077608	-2.519798733	0.000925069	0.020197348	0.016878459	994	tags=29%, list=8%, signal=27%	43283/39020/42253/41087/42791/35862/43256/43222/38419/2768679/36047/50126/32099/38858/43596/43598/39870/43599/39869/38408/37184
dme03430	Mismatch repair	17	-0.739592638	-2.194604841	0.000388802	0.013877119	0.011596789	2036	tags=94%, list=17%, signal=78%	34423/38492/40607/37290/40972/35364/32113/34842/34550/32763/35119/34892/36705/39746/35796/39654
dme03440	Homologous recombination	22	-0.743128459	-2.347771274	0.000426621	0.013877119	0.011596789	2500	tags=91%, list=21%, signal=72%	41839/44259/31044/41366/40972/35364/32113/41746/31565/43577/33507/34892/34565/39746/35236/48309/318579/37564/36136/35937
dme03460	Fanconi anemia pathway	23	-0.774869364	-2.492096398	0.000429553	0.013877119	0.011596789	2441	tags=96%, list=20%, signal=77%	31044/35895/41366/40972/35364/36654/40965/32113/41231/38079/31565/43577/40438/31373/36705/35236/2768674/35796/318579/32608/36136/36199